

The Coupling Series, Photon Jets and The Higgs – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of the coupling constants series using the framework of Variational curvature, in particular using the first and second representations of the equation, net variations and spin, it is possible to construct a setting in which photon and anti-photon pair eliminate each other to create a spin zero particle, or the higgs boson.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.13)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.14)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma - \gamma \quad (1.15)$$

Since we have two photons pairing, photon and anti-photon, both were emitted from fermion clusters with opposite sign:

$$\left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

$$\left[2N_2 - \frac{1}{2}\right] - \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 - 1$$

The result of combining the photons would be again, a cluster with zero spin as we analyzed in the theory. Since the higgs boson has spin zero, the conclusion is that two opposite in charge sign photons, can give rise to a spin zero particle such as the higgs. It is the case with photon jets, but here analysis is via the primordial coupling constants series, which makes it easy to understand.

$$2N_2 - 1 + 2N_2 + 1 = 4N_2 \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma\gamma^- \rightarrow H^0$$

Spin 0 (2N variations) →

Matter with spin ($\frac{1}{2}$)(2N variations + 3) →

Bosons with spin (1) (2N variations + 3) + N_V →

Bosons with higher spin integers(2N variations + 3) + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + ... →

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)